

Socialization of consumer protection against products that harming society

Doris Rahmat * and Santoso Budi NU

Slamet Riyadi University of Surakarta.

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Abstract

Despite the fact that the consumer protection law number 8 of 1999 has been issued on consumer protection, which guarantees the rights of consumers. Sometimes ignored by business actors and sadly consumers also act indifferently in fighting for the rights that must be obtained by consumers who have been protected by law.

In Consumer Protection Act Article 29 paragraph 1 of Law No. 8 of 1999 concerning consumer protection it is stated that "the government is responsible for fostering the implementation of consumer protection which guarantees the acquisition of consumer rights and business actors as well as the implementation of the obligations of consumers and business actors.

Keywords: *Protection; Consumers*

1. Introduction

The Principle of Consumer Protection in Indonesia :

- Benefit Principle; mandates that all efforts in the implementation of consumer protection must provide the maximum benefit for the interests of consumers and business actors as a whole,
- The principle of justice that is a participation of all people can be realized maximally and provide opportunities for consumers and business actors to obtain their rights and carry out their obligations fairly,
- Principle of Balance; provide a balance between the interests of consumers, business actors, and the government in a material and spiritual sense,
- Principles of Consumer Security and Safety; provide guarantees for security and safety to consumers in the use, use and utilization of goods and/or services that are consumed or used;
- The principle of legal certainty; both business actors and consumers obey the law and obtain justice in the implementation of consumer protection, and the state guarantees legal certainty

In Article 3 of Law No. 8 of 1999 is concerning consumer protection. Purpose:

- Increase the awareness, ability and independence of consumers to protect themselves; b. elevating the dignity of consumers by preventing them from the negative excesses of the use of goods and/or services. increasing the empowerment of consumers in choosing, determining, and demanding their rights as consumers; d. create a consumer protection system that contains elements of legal certainty and information disclosure as well as access to information; e. raise awareness of business actors regarding the importance of consumer protection so as to grow an honest and responsible attitude in doing business; f. improve the quality of goods and/or

* Corresponding author: Doris Rahmat
Slamet Riyadi University of Surakarta.

services that ensure the continuity of the business of producing goods and/or services, health, comfort, security and safety of consumers.

The main cause of consumer weakness which the author discusses in the background is the level of consumer awareness of their rights is still low. This is mainly due to the low price of goods and the complicated or time-consuming Complaint Process, which is why it

Explicitly stated in Protection Law the: Business actors in offering goods and/or services intended to be traded are prohibited from offering, promoting, advertise or make false or misleading statements regarding: a. the price or tariff of an item and/or service; b. the use of goods and/or services; c. conditions, dependents, guarantees, rights or compensation for goods and/or services; d. offer discounts or attractive prizes offered; e. the dangers of using goods and/or services.”

A lot of what we find in minimarkets, the prices listed do not match the prices paid at the cashier, when consumers know that many of them choose to be silent and don't ask "why are the prices different". In the case that the business actor clearly harms consumer.

2. methods

Participants in legal counseling are members of the general public, namely PKK Malangjiwan women. The problem faced is that they do not know how to protect the socialization of consumer protection against products that are detrimental to society

The implementation is carried out by the lecture method followed by a question and answer session with the participants and good relationship between participants and the lecturers in the context of legal counseling, as well as to ensure understanding of mothers as consumers who experience products that harm them.

3. Feasibility of higher education

Community service is one of the tasks of Lecturers in implementing the Tri Dharma of Higher Education. Legal counseling as a form of community service is carried out by a team from the UNISRI Faculty of Law who have competencies according to the material presented, namely about socialization

Legal Counseling is carried out on an ongoing basis according to the schedule set by the University through LPPM so as to increase the experience for team members.

4. Results achieved

Legal counseling activities carried out directly or lectures went well and were fun. The participants were enthusiastic to know and understand the material presented. This really supports the delivery of the material well to the participants.

The results achieved are that the participants gain knowledge about consumer protection.

The legal system Indonesia as a system of rules that applies in the State of Indonesia is such a complex and extensive system of rules, which consists of legal elements, where the legal elements are interrelated with each other, influence each other and complement each other. In developments in the business world, there are many mistakes, both intentional and unintentional, by business actors, which often harm consumers, when the consumer feels disadvantaged in reporting to the business actor, the consumer often gets unpleasant treatment. When the consumer wants to get his rights, he is even trapped by rules that are not stated beforehand, for example, the goods purchased cannot be exchanged if there is no agreement or writing in the store. As for the writing, it is made very small in the bottom corner of the receipt so that it cannot be read by consumers. There are several business actors who make tricks so that consumers cannot complain. In fact, we often hear the slogan "consumer is king" which in reality seems to be fading. Let alone being treated by the king, as consumers, they are often victims compared to business actors. In order for the position of consumers to look strong and equal, a law was born that regulates consumer protection.

In Consumer Protection Act Article 29 paragraph 1 of Law No. 8 of 1999 concerning consumer protection it is stated that "the government is responsible for fostering the implementation of consumer protection which guarantees the acquisition of consumer rights" and business actors as well as the implementation of the obligations of consumers and business actors.

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A lot of what we find in minimarkets, the prices listed do not match the prices paid at the cashier, when consumers know that many of them choose to be silent and don't ask "why are the prices different". What the business actor does is clearly detrimental to consumers.

Even though the consumer protection law has been around for a long time, which is the legal umbrella for consumers, consumers are not yet aware of it. There are still many consumers who think this law is really needed when they are in trouble with the law. In fact, if consumers are more concerned with their rights as regulated by law, it will be consumers who are treated unfairly and how to fight for the rights

The rights of consumers and business actors are as well as carrying out the obligations of consumers and business actors.

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Figure 1 Socialization of Consumer Protection Act Article 29 paragraph 1 of Law No. 8 of 1999

5. Conclusion

In Consumer Protection Act Article 29 paragraph 1 of Law No. 8 of 1999 concerning consumer protection it is stated that "the government is responsible for fostering the implementation of consumer protection that guarantees the acquisition of consumer rights and business actors as well as the implementation of consumer and business actors' obligations.

Suggestion

Legal counseling should be carried out on an ongoing basis, continuously carried out in all circles of society so that the dissemination of information can be carried out evenly. Legal counseling can be done directly face to face or through online or online media.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of Interest.

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